

Cognitive Impairment among Elderly in Urban Slums of Bangalore- A Community Based Cross Sectional StudyN. Ramakrishna Reddy¹, Kishore S. G.², S. Aswinkumar³, D. Shanmugapriya⁴, C. Karthik⁵, D. Jaiganesh⁶, A.R.C. Poornima⁷, A.R. Adhilakshmi⁸¹Professor of Community Medicine, Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute, Bangalore,²Assistant Professor of Community Medicine, Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute, Bangalore,³Associate Professor of Transfusion Medicine, Chengalpattu Medical College, Chengalpattu⁴Assistant Professor of Community Medicine, Coimbatore Medical College, Coimbatore⁵Assistant Professor of Community Medicine, Madras Medical College, Chennai⁶Associate Professor of Community Medicine, Chengalpattu Medical College, Chengalpattu⁷Assistant Professor of Dermatology, Madras Medical College, Chennai⁸Associate Professor of Community Medicine, Madras Medical College, Chennai

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Abstract:**Background:** Global population ageing is an important challenge and opportunity faced by all countries. The changing demographic profile has thrown many new challenges in the social, economic and political domains. The mental health being one of the neglected aspect of geriatric health in many parts of the world, plays a crucial role in developing Healthy Ageing. Cognitive impairment, an age-related condition, is often considered a precursor to more serious diseases such as depression/dementia/Alzheimer's disease.**Objectives:** To determine the prevalence of cognitive impairment among elderly and to describe the pattern of cognitive impairment.**Materials and Methods:** A cross-sectional community based study was carried among in urban slums of Bangalore, 150 elderly individuals aged more than 60years and who were not previously diagnosed to have any cognitive impairment were screened using Cognitive Assessment toolkit. Data entered in Epidata and analysed using SPSS software version 23.**Results:** The prevalence of cognitive impairment among the elderly participants in urban slums using GPCOG indicated that 8% of participants scored between 0-4, suggesting probable cognitive impairment and approximately 14% of participants scored ≤ 4 in MIS. 13.3% of participants scored below 4 in Mini Cog scale and 16% of participants scored above the critical threshold of 3.38, indicating cognitive concerns. Significant association was found with age. As age increases, there was a significant reduction in cognitive level and significantly higher prevalence with females compared to males ($p < 0.05$)**Conclusion:** Significant prevalence of cognitive impairment among elderly individuals in urban slums with prevalence rates ranging from 8% to 17.3%. Each tool, including GPCOG, MIS, Mini-Cog, IQCODE, and AD8, highlighted age as a key factor in cognitive decline.**Keywords:** Elderly, Cognitive Impairment, Cognitive Assessment toolkit.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Global population ageing is an important challenge and opportunity faced by all countries. The changing demographic profile has thrown many new challenges in the social, economic and political domains. The mental health being one of the neglected aspect of geriatric health in many parts of the world, plays a crucial role in developing Healthy Ageing. Cognitive impairment, an age-related condition, is often considered a precursor to more serious diseases such as depression/dementia/Alzheimer's disease in up to

one third of cases. In cognitive impairment, the cognitive deficit is less severe than in dementia and normal daily function and independence are generally maintained. [2] Dementia is one of the major causes of disability in older people. Cognitive impaired are at 10 times higher risk of developing Dementia. [3] As India's population ages, there is increasing concern about cognitive impairment, particularly dementia. The World Health Organization (WHO) has estimated that more than 55 million people worldwide have

dementia, with a large percentage of cases (60%) taking place in low- and middle-income nations. A significant percentage of the elderly population, who deal with various health issues, live in urban slums. Poor living circumstances, poor nutrition, limited access to healthcare services, and low health literacy all contribute to cognitive impairment in these locations, making this population especially susceptible to undiagnosed and untreated cognitive decline. Screening for early detection enables interventions that can enhance quality of life, lessen the strain on caregivers and healthcare systems, and delay the rate of cognitive deterioration. Hence this study was carried out to determine the prevalence of cognitive impairment among elderly and to describe the pattern of cognitive impairment among them in selected urban slums of Bangalore.

Materials and Methods:

A community based cross-sectional study was carried out among 150 individuals more than 60 years who were not previously diagnosed to have any cognitive impairment in selected urban areas of Bangalore. Confirmation of the age was done by following using one or more criteria: An authentic document/certificate, Retirement year (if retired), Year of marriage + gap period of his/her eldest child birth + Age of eldest son/daughter = Age of the subject, Date of birth before independence year (1947) of India respect to freedom of India, Self and family assessment of the subject. Those having any problem suggesting significant organic pathology like head injury, seizure, mental retardation, substance abuse, etc., or having

physical health problems which affects functioning of daily living and having problems with speech, hearing, and vision, which can impede the interview were excluded. Eligible individuals were screened for the cognitive impairment using Cognitive Assessment toolkit. [5]

Cognitive Assessment toolkit consists of Patient assessment tools - GP COG, MINI COG & MIS and Informant assessment of patient- IQCODE AND AD8. Values of Patient: Mini-Cog ≤ 3 or GPCOG (5-8 score is indeterminate without informant) or Informant: Short IQCODE ≥ 3.38 or AD8 ≥ 2 or GPCOG informant score ≤ 3 with patient score was considered as impairment and needs further evaluation. Data was analyzed using SPSS software version 23. Details regarding overall prevalence of cognitive impairment among elderly and its distribution pattern in relationship to literacy, socio economic status and other variables were analysed.

The chi-square test and Pearson correlation were used to determine the association of cognitive impairment with various socio demographic parameters.

Results:

Community based cross sectional study, carried out to assess the cognitive function of the elderly populations in urban slums with results from similar studies using GPCOG, MIS, Mini-Cog, IQCODE, and AD8 tools are as follows. Out of 150 respondents 95 (63.3%) were female and 55 (36.7%) were males.

Table 1: Age wise distribution of the study participants

Age category	Frequency N=150	Percentage
60-64	57	38
65-69	53	35.3
70-74	25	16.7
≥ 75	15	10

Median age is 65 years and it ranges from 60 to 90 years. 76.7% belongs to upper lower class with around 46.7% were illiterate and 42% were widowed.

Table 2: Distribution of GPCOG Score among study participants

Score	Frequency (%)
STEP 1	
9	86(57.3)
5-8	52(34.7)
0-4	12(8)
STEP 2- informant interview	
0-3	29(19.4)
4-6	121(80.6.)

Patient interview of GPCOG shows that 8% of the participants had score between 0 to 4, indicating potential cognitive impairment, however on further evaluation of the participants by enquiring the informant, 19.4% has cognitive impairment.

Table 3: Distribution based on MIS score and MINI COG

MIS	Frequency (%)
≤4	21 (14%)
5-8	129 (86%)
MINI COG	
<4	20 (13.3%)
4-5	130 (86.7%)

The Modified Informant Score (MIS) test showed that 14% scored ≤4, indicating possible cognitive concerns and remaining 86% of participants scored between 5 and 8. The Mini-Cog Scores indicated that 86.7% of participants scored between 4 and 5, reflecting normal cognitive functioning, whereas 13.3% scored <4, suggesting possible cognitive impairment.

Table 4: Distribution based on IQCODE

IQCODE	Frequency (%)
3	118 (78.7%)
3.1-3.5	20 (13.3%)
3.6-4.0	11 (7.3%)
4.0-5.0	1 (0.7%)

<3.38- 84% and >3.38- 16%

78.7% of the study participants scored around 3, suggesting normal cognitive functioning. 3.1–3.5 were observed in 13.3% of participants, while 7.3% scored between 3.6–4.0, and 0.7% scored between 4.0–5.0. 16% of the participants scored below 3.38 indicating significant impairment in memory.

Table 5: Distribution based on AD8

AD8	Frequency (%)
0-1	82.7%
2to8	17.3%

82.7% of participants scored between 0 and 1 on the AD8 tool, suggesting no significant cognitive concerns where 17.3% of participants scored between 2-8, indicating possible cognitive impairment.

Table 6: Association between age and MIS score

Age Category	MIS		Total	P=0.000 P<0.05
	≤4	5-8		
60-64	0	57	57	
65-69	5	48	53	
70-74	6	19	25	
≥75	10	5	15	
TOTAL	21	129	150	

Significant association was found between MIS and Age ($p=0.000$). Participants in the oldest age group (≥ 75) showed a higher frequency of lower MIS scores (≤ 4), with 10 out of 15 participants falling into this range.

Table 7: Association between age and AD8 Score

Age Category	AD8		Total	P=0.000 P<0.05
	0-1	2-8		
60-64	56	1	57	
65-69	47	6	53	
70-74	17	8	25	
≥75	4	11	15	
Total	124	26	150	

There is a significant association ($p=0.000$) between age and AD8 scores. In the 60–64 age group, 98.2% scored between 0 and 1 on the AD8, with only 1 participant scoring between 2 and 8. The oldest age group (≥ 75), however, had 73.3% of participants scoring between 2 and 8, indicating age-related increase in cognitive impairment.

Table 8: Association between gender and Scores

Gender	MIS		Total	P
	≤4	5-8		
Female	18	77	95	P=0.027 P<0.05
Male	3	52	55	
Gender	AD8		Total	P
	0-1	2-8		
Female	74	21	95	P=0.042 P<0.05
Male	50	5	55	

Significant association was observed between gender and both MIS and AD8 scores, whereas no significant association was observed between gender and GPCOG. 18 out of 95 female participants scored ≤4, compared to only 3 out of 55 males, suggesting gender differences in cognitive performance. In terms of AD8 scores, 22.1% of females scored in the 2–8 range compared to 9.1% of males, with p-value of 0.042, indicating that females in this population experience higher rates of cognitive decline.

Table 9: Association between Marital status and Score

Marital status	MIS		Total	P
	≤4	5-8		
Married	7	80	87	P=0.017 P<0.05
Widowed	14	49	63	
	AD8		Total	P
	0-1	2-8		
Married	78	9	87	P=0.009 P<0.05
Widowed	46	17	63	

Widowed participants showed a higher frequency of scores ≤4 (22.2%) compared to married participants (8.0%), with a p-value of 0.017, suggesting an association between being widowed and lower cognitive scores. Among widowed participants, 27.0% scored between 2 and 8 on the AD8, compared to 10.3% of married participants, indicating a potential role of marital status on cognitive function. A strong correlation was found with AD8 (0.531), while moderate correlations appeared with MIS (0.519), GPCOG Step 1 (0.396) and Step 2 (0.440), Mini-Cog (0.509), and IQCODE (0.511), all suggesting that older age is associated with greater cognitive impairment across multiple assessment tools.

Discussion

Early identification of cognitive impairment is crucial for slow disease progression and improve the quality of life of the people. Among the 150 respondents majority being illiterate, the overall prevalence through combination of cognitive testing and information from a person who has frequent contact with the patient, were found to be ranging from 8% to 17.3% depending on the scale used.

In the present study, 57.3% scored within the normal range (score of 9) in Step 1 in GPCOG scale, while 8% scored lower (0–4), indicating probable impairment. This is similar to the findings by Brodaty et al., [6] who reported that about 60% of their elderly population scored similarly, identifying age as a significant factor influencing

GPCOG scores. Age correlation with GPCOG Step 1 and Step 2 yielded moderate values (0.396 and 0.440, respectively), which is similar to the study by Cullen et al., [7] who found that GPCOG is moderately sensitive to age-related decline but more so when combined with informant responses. With regards to MIS score, 86% scored in the range of 5–8, while 14% scored ≤4, reflecting potential memory impairment. Similar results was observed in the study by Bushchke et al [8] that MIS is a highly reliable tool across various socioeconomic and educational backgrounds, reporting a 12% rate of impairment, which closely aligns with the current study findings.

86.7% of the study participants scored within the normal range (4–5), with 13.3% scoring <4 with MINI COG scale, indicative of possible cognitive impairment. Similar results was seen in the study by Borson et al. [9] found that Mini-Cog, with around 15% of participants in their study showing impairment. Similar results was found in another study by Rinaldi et al [10] which showed that 12% of participants showed impairment, again consistent with the findings. These parallels reinforce that Mini-Cog remains a dependable screening measure in varied socioeconomic and cultural contexts, detecting early signs of cognitive decline with a minimal influence from demographic variations. In the current study, the IQCODE scores reveal 84% scoring below 3.38 (considered within normal limits) and 16% above 3.38 (indicating cognitive concerns). Similar findings were reported by Tang MX et al, [11]

showing an 1.3% to 7.9%, showing higher rate of significant cognitive impairment as the age increases. This finding underscores that IQCODE, with its reliance on informant feedback, effectively highlights cognitive changes influenced by age without strong demographic bias. 17.3% of participants scored between 2–8 in AD8 scale, suggesting impairment, while 82.7% scored 0–1, indicative of normal function. Galvin et al. [12] found that AD8, through brief informant interviews, provided efficient cognitive screening, with around 20% scoring within impairment thresholds in a general elderly population, The age-related correlation (0.531) you observed also aligns with these studies, highlighting AD8's potential for early identification of cognitive issues in diverse settings, making it an ideal screening choice in urban slum populations. Most of them had problem with memory component than compared to other components of cognition.

As age progresses we could notice more impairment in other components of cognition such as Judgment, Decision making, Reasoning and problem solving. Most of the family members have not realized the importance of early cognitive change among their elder persons in the family and almost none have sought healthcare provider for their impairment.

Conclusion

Overall, these findings suggest that the prevalence of cognitive impairment in this population ranges from 8% to 17.3%, depending on the assessment tool used. This highlights a significant concern for cognitive health among the elderly in urban slum areas, necessitating targeted screening and intervention strategies to address cognitive decline in this vulnerable population.

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